

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE, ACTIVITY, AND ESG ON FIRM VALUE IN MANUFACTURING SECTOR COMPANIES LISTED ON THE IDX FOR THE 2021-2024 PERIOD

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the effect of capital structure, activity, and ESG on firm value in manufacturing sector companies listed on the IDX during the 2021-2024 period. Capital structure is measured using the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), activity is measured by Total Assets Turnover (TATO), ESG is measured using the Sustainalytics score, while firm value is measured by Price to Book Value (PBV). This study also incorporates profitability, measured by Return on Assets (ROA), and firm size as control variables. This research employs a quantitative approach with the unit of analysis consisting of manufacturing sector companies that meet the research criteria. The sample includes 44 companies with a total of 176 panel data observations obtained through purposive sampling. The data analysis technique used is panel data regression with the selected model being the Random Effect Model (REM). The results indicate that capital structure, as measured by DER, has a positive and significant effect on firm value. This finding suggests that the optimal use of debt can enhance firm value through tax shield benefits and by providing positive signals to investors. Conversely, activity, measured by TATO, shows a negative and insignificant effect on firm value, indicating that asset utilization efficiency has not been a primary consideration for investors in assessing manufacturing companies during the research period. Meanwhile, ESG demonstrates a positive but insignificant effect on firm value, suggesting that sustainability practices and good corporate governance have received a positive response from the market, although their impact on increasing firm value is not yet statistically strong. This study is expected to serve as a reference for companies, investors, and regulators in understanding the factors influencing firm value and to provide a foundation for future research.

Keywords: Capital Structure, Activity, ESG, Firm Value, Manufacturing Companies.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2018, the world's two largest economies, the United States (US) and China, imposed import tariffs on each other, which later escalated into the US-China trade war (Itakura, 2020). The conflict began with accusations from the administration of former President Donald Trump that China had engaged in unfair trade practices, including intellectual property theft and industrial subsidies (Rastuti & Khoirudin, 2025). The reciprocal tariff measures illustrated how quickly economic conflicts can expand and create uncertainty in global markets. This uncertainty also generated psychological impacts on investors and influenced investment decisions as well as stock market movements in

Indonesia (Rastuti & Khoirudin, 2025).

Based on data from the Indonesia Central Securities Depository (KSEI), domestic investors dominate the Indonesian capital market with a composition of more than 50%, and this percentage has continued to increase over the years (Natalia, 2025). This shift in investor dominance reflects changes in the capital market structure alongside the movement of the Composite Stock Price Index (IHSG) during the 2021-2024 period.

Figure 1.1 Movement of the Composite Stock Price Index (IHS) 2021–2024

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

The graph above illustrates the annual movement of the IHS from 2021 to 2024 based on data from Refinitiv (Setiawati, 2024). The fluctuations in the IHS indicate dynamic conditions in the Indonesian capital market, which affect corporate performance and valuation across various sectors, including the manufacturing sector, one of the main contributors to Indonesia's economy.

The manufacturing sector is one of the primary drivers of the national economy and one of the largest providers of employment in Indonesia (Manufacturing Indonesia, 2025). In 2024, this sector recorded the largest contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at 18.98% and absorbed 4% of the workforce in 2024 (Nafi, 2025). In addition, the manufacturing sector includes one of the highest numbers of companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), thus playing a significant role in overall market value formation. These conditions indicate that the manufacturing sector contributes to enhancing firm value in the Indonesian capital market.

Firm value is an important indicator in demonstrating performance to investors (Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan, 2025). It reflects the level of investor confidence in a company's prospects and market position. The higher the confidence, the greater the investor's perception of the company's growth potential. Besides stock prices, firm value is commonly proxied by the Price to Book Value (PBV) ratio (Nurhidayati et al., 2021). The following figure presents the average firm value of manufacturing companies listed on the IDX during the 2021–2024 period, measured by comparing the market price of a stock to its book value based on IDX data.

Figure 1.2 Average Firm Value of Manufacturing Sector Companies 2021–2024

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

Based on the graph above, the average firm value of manufacturing companies fluctuated during the 2021–2024 period. The fluctuations in PBV may be influenced by financial factors such as capital structure (DER) and activity (TATO), as well as non-financial factors such as ESG implementation (Dinarjito, 2025; Mahirun et al., 2025).

An optimal capital structure maximizes stock prices through an ideal debt ratio (Sihombing et al., 2025). Capital structure reflects how a company finances its operations and investments, as well as the extent of its reliance on external funding sources. The ratio commonly used to assess borrowing influence from creditors is the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) (Nurhidayati et al., 2021). This ratio measures the proportion of debt relative to equity in a company's capital structure, illustrating the extent to which a company uses borrowed funds compared to its own capital. An optimal DER indicates a balance between debt risk and return potential, which ultimately affects firm value.

Activity ratios measure a company's effectiveness in utilizing its total assets (Vania & Tarmizi, 2022). These ratios evaluate how efficiently a company uses its assets to support daily operations. One commonly used ratio is Total Assets Turnover (TATO), which measures the company's performance in managing total assets to generate sales or revenue (Mahirun et al., 2025). A high TATO indicates optimal asset utilization, which can positively influence firm value, whereas a low TATO may suggest underutilized or less productive assets.

In addition to financial performance, non-financial performance is increasingly considered by investors in making investment decisions. This indicates that non-financial factors, such as sustainability, are gaining greater attention in corporate evaluation (Dinarjito, 2025). In recent years, ESG practices have emerged as an important component of business strategy (Chen et al., 2025). This development is supported by Financial Services Authority Regulation (POJK) No. 51/POJK.03/2017 concerning the Implementation of Sustainable Finance for Financial Service Institutions, Issuers, and Public Companies. Article 2 paragraph (1) states that financial institutions, issuers, and public companies are required to implement sustainable finance in their business activities. Meanwhile, Article 10 paragraph (1) requires companies to prepare periodic sustainability reports (Financial Services Authority of the Republic of Indonesia, 2017). This

regulation underscores the importance of ESG practices and sustainability reporting as part of corporate governance that can enhance transparency and firm value. Therefore, ESG scores of manufacturing companies have become important indicators for investors in assessing company prospects and risks beyond traditional financial performance.

Previous studies by Endraria & Sagara (2025); Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan (2025); Mahirun et al. (2025); Nurhidayati et al. (2021); and Sihombing et al. (2025) found that capital structure has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Conversely, studies by H. Ahmad et al. (2022); Wahyuni & Gani (2022); and Yuliandhari & Nurramadhani (2024) reported a negative and significant effect. Meanwhile, research by Faradila & Effendi (2023); Ferriswara et al. (2022); Kristantiningtyas & Dewi (2024); Pustika et al. (2022); and Valencia (2025) concluded that capital structure has no significant effect on firm value.

Furthermore, studies by Ferriswara et al. (2022); Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan (2025); Mahirun et al. (2025); and Siregar et al. (2025) found that activity positively and significantly affects firm value. In contrast, research by N. Ahmad et al. (2023); Ni & Cheng (2025); and Valencia (2025) reported a negative and significant effect. However, studies by H. Ahmad et al. (2022); Colline (2022); Sihombing et al. (2025); and Uzliawati et al. (2023) indicated no significant effect.

Similarly, research by Huang et al. (2025); Mulyana et al. (2025); Rahmaniati & Ekawati (2024); Rashwan et al. (2025); and Uzliawati et al. (2023) showed that ESG has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Meanwhile, studies by Al-Tarawneh et al. (2024); Ruan & Liu (2021); Yori & Rahmawati (2025); and Zhang (2024) found a negative and significant effect. On the other hand, research by Chen et al. (2025); Dorothy & Endri (2024); Liu & Lee (2025); Shahrin et al. (2023); and Zhou et al. (2022) concluded that ESG has no significant effect on firm value.

These inconsistent findings create a significant research gap that warrants further investigation, particularly regarding the direction and significance of the relationships. Moreover, there remains a limited number of studies specifically examining Indonesian manufacturing companies during the most recent period of 2021–2024, especially concerning the influence of capital structure, activity, and ESG on firm value. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by examining and analyzing the effect of capital structure, activity, and ESG on firm value in manufacturing sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2021–2024 period.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Signaling Theory

The trade-off theory was first proposed by Modigliani and Miller in 1963. It explains that a company can achieve an optimal capital structure by balancing the tax benefits of debt against the costs of financial distress (Modigliani & Miller, 1963). This theory emphasizes that debt has two sides: it provides advantages in the

form of tax savings, but it also creates risks if used excessively. Therefore, companies must determine an optimal capital structure to maximize firm value without increasing the risk of bankruptcy.

2.2. Optimal Capital Structure Theory

According to Brigham & Houston (2019), the optimal capital structure is the one that maximizes the intrinsic value of a company's shares. An optimal structure is achieved when the balance between debt and equity results in the lowest Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC). A proper capital structure helps increase firm value and maximize shareholder wealth. However, an excessive proportion of debt increases bankruptcy risk, while excessive reliance on equity may reduce the potential return for shareholders.

2.3. Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory, proposed by Freeman (2010), emphasizes that companies must consider and fulfill the interests of various parties that influence business operations. These stakeholders include employees, customers, suppliers, governments, communities, and the surrounding environment. According to this theory, a company's success can be measured by its ability to create value and mutually beneficial relationships for all stakeholders. Companies must balance economic, social, and environmental interests to sustain long-term business continuity.

2.4. Relationship Among Variables and Hypothesis Development

2.4.1 Capital Structure and Firm Value.

When capital structure is managed properly, companies are able to optimize firm value (Nurhidayati et al., 2021). Research by Endraria & Sagara (2025) shows that an increase in capital structure can enhance firm value as long as the debt level remains within an optimal range. This finding is consistent with Mahirun et al. (2025), who found that capital structure has a positive and significant effect on firm value among companies included in the IDX80 index on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2019–2022 period. Similarly, Sihombing et al. (2025) revealed that the use of debt in capital structure increased firm value in construction companies listed on the IDX during the quarterly period of 2013–2020. Therefore, the first hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H1: Capital Structure has a positive and significant effect on Firm Value.

2.4.2 Activity and Firm Value.

A higher asset turnover ratio indicates increased sales value, meaning that assets are utilized optimally to meet market demand (Sihombing et al., 2025). Research by Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan (2025) shows that company activity has a positive and significant effect on firm value in the real estate sector in Indonesia during the 2017–2023 period. Similar findings were reported by Mahirun et al. (2025), who found that company activity positively and significantly affects firm value among companies listed in the IDX80 index during 2019–2022. Therefore, the second hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H2: Activity has a positive and significant effect on Firm Value.

2.4.3 ESG and Firm Value.

ESG can enhance investor confidence, which is reflected in rising stock prices as investors perceive the company as more stable, ethical, and capable of managing long-term risks (Dinarjito, 2025). Companies that focus on ESG aspects tend to achieve higher firm value (Rahmaniati & Ekawati, 2024). Huang et al. (2025) found that ESG ratings have a positive and significant relationship with market value among companies listed in China from 2008 to 2021. This finding is consistent with Rahmaniati & Ekawati (2024), who reported that ESG scores have a positive and significant effect on firm value measured by PBV. Furthermore, Rashwan et al. (2025) found that ESG is positively and significantly related to firm value among public companies in the MENA region during 2017–2022. Based on these findings, the third hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H3: ESG has a positive and significant effect on Firm Value.

Figure 2.1 Research Conceptual Framework

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

3. RESEARCH MEHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study uses a quantitative research design to investigate the effect of Capital Structure (X1), Activity (X2), and ESG (X3) on Firm Value (Y), with Profitability (C1) and Firm Size (C2) as a control variable.

3.2 Population and Sample

The population in this study consists of 475 manufacturing sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2021–2024 period. The sample was determined using purposive sampling, which involves selecting companies based on specific criteria established by the researcher (Sekaran & Bougie, 2021). The criteria used in this study are as follows:

- 1) Manufacturing sector companies that were consecutively listed on the IDX during the 2021–2024 period.
- 2) Manufacturing sector companies that had ESG scores published by Morningstar Sustainalytics in 2024.
- 3) Manufacturing sector companies that published complete annual reports during the 2021–2024 period.

Table 3.1 Research Sample Criteria

No.	Description	Total
Population: Manufacturing sector companies listed on the IDX during 2021–2024		475
1.	Manufacturing companies not consecutively listed on the IDX during 2021–2024.	(101)
2.	Manufacturing companies consecutively listed but without ESG scores published by Morningstar Sustainalytics in 2024.	(329)
3.	Manufacturing companies with ESG scores but without complete annual reports during 2021–2024.	(1)
Research Sample		44
Total Observations (n x research period) (44 x 4 years)		176

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

3.3 Data Collection

The data collection technique used in this study is documentation through secondary data. Data were obtained for the 2021–2024 period from companies' annual reports and ESG scores from Morningstar Sustainalytics. Annual reports were sourced from each company's official website, while ESG scores were obtained from the official Morningstar Sustainalytics website. This study uses panel data, combining cross-sectional data (several sample companies) and time-series data (four-year observation period). However, prior studies (Wedajo et al., 2024; Ratsimiveh et al., 2020) indicate that ESG scores are relatively stable over time. Supporting this, OECD findings show that 88% of companies in the top ESG quintile in 2010 remained in the top quintile in 2018 (Wedajo et al., 2024). Therefore, this study uses the most recent ESG score available (2024) to represent the company's ESG practices during the 2021–2024 period.

3.4 Measures

Table 3.2 Research Variable Operations

Variable	Operational Definition	Indicator	Scala	Source
Dependent Variable				
Firm Value (Y)	The assessment given by investors regarding the company's success and performance as reflected in its market stock price.	$PBV = \frac{\text{Market Price per Share}}{\text{Book Value per Share}}$	Ratio	Hidayat & Khotimah (2022); Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan (2025); and Sihombing et al. (2025)
Independent Variables				
Capital Structure (X1)	The proportion between equity and debt owned by the company.	$DER = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Equity}}$	Ratio	Brigham & Houston (2019; Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan (2025); and Permata et al. (2025)
Activity (X2)	A measure of the efficiency and effectiveness of a company's operational activities in generating sales.	$TATO = \frac{\text{Total Sales}}{\text{Total Assets}}$	Ratio	Brigham & Houston (2019); Colline (2022); and Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan (2025)
ESG (X3)	A framework that integrates environmental, social, and governance dimensions into business evaluation, shifting the focus from purely financial metrics to sustainability-related factors.	$ESG \text{ Score} = 100 - \text{ESG Risk Score}$	Interval	Erhart (2022)
Control Variables				
Profitability (C1)	A financial ratio that reflects a company's effectiveness in generating profit relative to its assets.	$ROA = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Assets}}$	Ratio	Ferriswara et al. (2022); Jatmiko et al. (2025); and Valenci (2025)
Firm Size (C2)	A measurement indicating the scale of a company, used as a consideration in firm valuation.	$\text{Firm Size} = \text{Ln}(\text{Total Assets})$	Ratio	Mulyana et al. (2025); Rahmaniati & Ekawati (2024); and Valencia (2025)

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

3.5 Data Analysis

Data analysis aims to identify and measure variations within a set of variables (Hair et al., 2019). At the data analysis stage, the collected data are statistically analyzed to determine whether the proposed hypotheses are supported by the research findings (Sekaran & Bougie, 2021). The analytical technique employed in this study is panel data regression analysis using Stata 17 statistical software. The analysis procedures include outlier identification, descriptive statistical analysis, classical assumption tests, regression model selection, panel data regression analysis, hypothesis testing, coefficient of determination testing, and robustness testing.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Identification Outlier

This study applied a 5% winsorization method to the firm value and capital structure variables that were identified as containing extreme data, with the aim of limiting the influence of outliers without removing observations. Winsorization was performed by adjusting values below the 5th percentile to the 5th percentile value and values above the 95th percentile to the 95th percentile value (Farina et al., 2025; Wu et al., 2025).

Table 4.1 Data Distribution Statistics of Firm Value Variable

	Before 5% Winsorize				After 5% Winsorize			
	Y (NP)		X1 (SM)		Y (NP)		X1 (SM)	
	Percentil	Smallest	Percentil	Smallest	Percentil	Smallest	Percentil	Smallest
1%	0,1761	0,1694	0,1252	0,1252	0,0498	0,0409	0,3301	0,3001
5%	0,3301	0,1761	0,1252	0,1252	0,1252	0,0498	0,3001	0,3301
10%	0,4917	0,1839	0,1409	0,1252	0,1409	0,0513	0,4917	0,3301
25%	0,8168	0,1962	0,3144	0,1252	0,3144	0,0882	0,81675	0,3301
50%	1,5895		0,69165		0,6917		1,5895	0,3301

		Largest		Largest		Largest		Largest
75%	3,5086	36,2848	1,1237	3,4127	1,1237	6,4659	3,5086	14,4577
90%	8,0065	39,8285	2,0583	3,4127	2,0583	8,9114	8,0065	14,4577
95%	14,4577	44,9570	3,4127	3,4127	3,4127	14,7795	14,4577	14,4577
99%	44,8570	362,5234	3,4127	3,4127	14,7795	190,3070	14,4577	14,4577
Std. Dev		27,8547		14,3502		3,6326		0,8293

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Before winsorization, the firm value variable had a very wide range (0.1694–362.5234) with extreme outliers, resulting in a high standard deviation (27.8547). After 5% winsorization, the range narrowed (0.3301–14.4577) and the standard deviation decreased to 3.6326, indicating a more stable distribution.

Similarly, the capital structure variable initially showed a wide range (0.0409–190.3070) and a high standard deviation (14.3502) due to extreme outliers. After 5% winsorization, the range narrowed (0.1252–3.4127) and the standard deviation declined to 0.8293.

4.2 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistics Analysis Results

	Y (NP)	X1 (SM)	X2 (AKTV)	X3 (ESG)	C1 (PROF)	C2 (SIZE)
Mean	3,0538	0,8831	0,9610	70,8932	0,0830	30,8229
Median	1,5895	0,6917	0,7942	70,3500	0,0705	30,6755
Max	14,4577	3,4127	3,8222	91,3000	0,4484	33,7900
Min	0,3301	0,1252	0,0103	49,7000	-0,0350	27,9008
Std. Dev.	3,6326	0,8293	0,7080	9,3833	0,0653	1,1472
Obs.	176	176	176	176	176	176

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

The descriptive statistics show that firm value has a mean of 3.0538 and a median of 1.5895, indicating a right-skewed distribution, with values ranging from 0.3301 to 14.4577 and a standard deviation of 3.6326, suggesting dispersion within a reasonable range. Capital structure also exhibits right-skewness, with a mean of 0.8831, median of 0.6917, minimum of 0.1252, maximum of 3.4127, and a standard deviation of 0.8293, indicating relatively low variability. Activity has a mean of 0.9610 and median of 0.7942, with values between 0.0103 and 3.8222 and a standard deviation of 0.7080, reflecting reasonable variation. ESG records a mean of 70.8932 and median of 70.3500, ranging from 49.7000 to 91.3000, with a standard deviation of 9.3833, indicating limited dispersion. Profitability shows a mean of 0.0830 and median of 0.0705, with a minimum of -0.0350, maximum of 0.4484, and standard deviation of 0.0653, suggesting relatively low variability. Meanwhile, firm size has a mean of 30.8229 and median of 30.6755, with values between 27.9008 and 33.7900 and a standard deviation of 1.1472, indicating dispersion within a reasonable range.

4.3 Classical Assumption Test

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test Results

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
X1 (NP)	1,23	0,8103
X2 (AKTV)	1,20	0,8334
X3 (ESG)	1,18	0,8504
C1 (PROF)	1,14	0,8768
C2 (SIZE)	1,12	0,8893
Mean VIF	1,17	

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the table above, all variables have a VIF value of 1.17, which is below the threshold of 10. This indicates that the regression model does not have multicollinearity issues, and therefore all independent variables can be used in the regression analysis.

Table 4.4 Heteroskedasticity Test Results

Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
Assumption: Normal error terms
Variable: Fitted valued of y
H0: Constant variance
chi2 (1) = 40,88
Prob > chi2 = 0,0000

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the Breusch-Pagan test results, the Prob > chi² value is 0.0000, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the error variance in the regression model is not constant, meaning the model exhibits heteroskedasticity. Therefore, to address potential bias in the standard errors due to heteroskedasticity, this study employs Cluster Robust Standard Errors (CRSE) in the regression model estimation.

Table 4.5 Autocorrelation Test Results

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data
H0: no first order autocorrelation
F (1, 43) = 21,561
Prob > F = 0,0000

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the Wooldridge test results, the Prob > F value is 0.0000, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the errors in the regression model are correlated, meaning the model exhibits autocorrelation. Therefore, to address potential bias in the standard errors due to autocorrelation, this study employs Cluster Robust Standard Errors (CRSE) in the regression model estimation.

4.4 Regression Model Section

Table 4.6 Model Selection Test Results

Model Selection Test	Probability	Selected Model
Chow Test	0,0000	FEM
Hausman Test	0,9986	REM
Lagrange Multiplier Test	0,0000	REM

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

The Chow test is conducted to determine the appropriate model between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and the Fixed Effect Model (FEM). Since the probability value of 0.0000 is lower than 0.05, FEM is selected. The Hausman test is then used to choose between FEM and the Random Effect Model (REM). With a probability value of 0.9986, which is greater than 0.05, REM is considered more appropriate. Furthermore, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test compares CEM and REM, and the probability value of 0.000, which is below 0.05, indicates that REM is the preferred model.

4.5 Hypothesis Testing

Table 4.7 t-Test Results

Y (NP)	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	p-value
X1 (SM)	1,8023	0,4848	3,7200	0,0000***
X2 (AKTV)	-0,3585	0,7205	-0,5000	0,6190
X3 (ESG)	0,0643	0,0506	1,2700	0,2040
C1 (PROF)	5,9520	2,8717	2,0700	0,0380**
C2 (SIZE)	-0,9861	0,4059	-2,4300	0,0150**
Year				
2022	0,3178	0,3542	0,9000	0,3700
2023	0,5934	0,4137	1,4300	0,1510
2024	0,6676	0,4447	1,5000	0,1330
Constant	26,7562	14,0104	1,9100	0,0560

***, **, *: Significant at 1%, 5%, and 10%

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the regression results, capital structure has a coefficient of 1.8023 with a p-value of 0.0000, indicating a positive and significant effect on firm value at the 1% level, so H1 is accepted. Activity has a coefficient of -0.3585 with a p-value of 0.6190, showing no significant effect; thus, H2 is rejected. Similarly, ESG has a coefficient of 0.0643 with a p-value of 0.2040, indicating no significant effect on firm value, so H3 is rejected. Among the control variables, profitability has a coefficient of 5.9520 with a p-value of 0.0380, demonstrating a positive and significant effect at the 5% level, meaning higher profitability increases firm value. In contrast, firm size has a coefficient of -0.9861 with a p-value of 0.0150, indicating a negative and significant effect at the 5% level. The year dummy variables for 2022, 2023, and 2024 are positive but not statistically significant, suggesting no significant time effects on firm value during the observation period.

4.6 Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 4.8 Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Observations	R-squared	Prob > F
176	0,4116	0,0002

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the table above, the R-squared value is 0.4116, indicating that 41.16% of the variation in firm value can be explained by the independent variables in the study model, while the remaining 58.84% is explained by other factors outside the model. In addition, the Prob > F value of 0.0002 indicates that the regression model is statistically significant as a whole.

4.7 Robustness Test

Table 4.9 Robustness Test Results

Y' (TQ)	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	p-value
X1 (SM)	0,1189	0,1568	0,7600	0,4480
X2 (AKTV)	-0,2188	0,3569	-0,6100	0,5400
X3 (ESG)	0,0323	0,0280	1,1500	0,2490
C1 (PROF)	3,5239	1,2363	2,8500	0,0040***
C2 (SIZE)	-0,5751	0,2816	-2,0400	0,0410**
Year				
2022	-0,0811	0,1294	-0,6300	0,5310
2023	0,0317	0,1472	0,2200	0,8300
2024	-0,0067	0,1859	-0,0400	0,9710
Constant	17,2654	9,6327	1,7900	0,0730

***, **, *: Significant at 1%, 5%, and 10%

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

The robustness test, which replaces the firm value proxy from Price to Book Value (PBV) with Tobin's Q, shows that most variables produce consistent results. Activity and ESG remain insignificant with the same direction of effect, while firm size also shows a consistent direction and significance level across both tests. Profitability continues to have a significant positive effect in both models, although its significance increases from the 5% level in the main test to the 1% level in the robustness test, indicating that its effect on firm value is robust. However, capital structure produces inconsistent results: it is positive and significant when using PBV but becomes insignificant when using Tobin's Q. This difference may arise because PBV is more sensitive to changes in equity composition, whereas Tobin's Q reflects total assets, which are relatively more stable. The year dummy variables remain insignificant, suggesting that firm value is influenced more by firm-specific factors than by time effects.

4.8 Discussion

4.8.1 The Effect of Capital Structure on Firm Value

The t-test results show that capital structure has a positive and significant effect on firm value, indicating that a more optimal use of debt can enhance firm value as long as it remains within an optimal range. The positive effect suggests that debt provides tax shield benefits and increases returns to shareholders, thereby strengthening firm value. These findings are consistent with the studies of Endraria & Sagara (2025); Khalifaturafi'ah & Setiawan (2025); Mahirun et al. (2025); Nurhidayati et al. (2021); and Sihombing et al. (2025), which demonstrate that capital structure positively and significantly affects firm value. In capital-intensive manufacturing firms, maintaining an appropriate balance between debt and equity is essential to support operational needs while controlling financial risk. This results support signaling theory, trade-off theory, and optimal capital structure theory. Signaling theory suggests that capital structure decisions send positive signals to the market about a firm's prospects. Trade-off theory emphasizes balancing the tax benefits of debt against bankruptcy risk. Meanwhile, optimal capital structure theory states that the right proportion of debt and equity can reduce the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) and maximize firm value.

4.8.2 The Effect of Activity on Firm Value

The t-test results indicate that activity does not have a significant effect on firm value, suggesting that asset utilization does not directly influence firm value within the sample. These findings

are consistent with prior studies by H. Ahmad et al. (2022), Colline (2022), Sihombing et al. (2025), and Uzliawati et al. (2023), which also find that activity does not significantly affect firm value. In manufacturing firms, although substantial fixed and current assets are held, activity levels do not necessarily reflect value creation because asset turnover does not always translate into added shareholder value and may be accompanied by high working capital needs and operational costs. In some cases, increased activity results from expansion or higher production capacity without matching market demand, leading to excess inventory or overcapacity. Moreover, high activity does not always indicate strong financial performance, as firms may experience high asset turnover alongside high debt or low profitability; therefore, investors tend to focus more on profitability and financial stability rather than activity levels when assessing firm value.

4.8.3 The Effect of ESG on Firm Value

The t-test results indicate that ESG does not have a significant effect on firm value, suggesting that within the sample, ESG implementation does not directly influence firm value. These findings are consistent with the studies of Chen et al. (2025), Dorothy & Endri (2024), Liu & Lee (2025), Shahrin et al. (2023), and Zhou et al. (2022), which show that although ESG has a positive direction of influence, the effect is not statistically significant. This implies that investors tend to prioritize financial indicators such as capital structure and profitability rather than ESG performance when evaluating firm value. In manufacturing firms, although ESG is important due to energy usage, emissions, and waste management, it may still be perceived primarily as regulatory compliance and operational responsibility rather than a key determinant of firm value.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study aims to examine the effect of capital structure, activity, and ESG on firm value in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2021–2024 period using panel data regression analysis. The results show that capital structure, measured by the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), has a positive and significant effect on firm value, indicating that the optimal use of debt can increase firm value through tax shield benefits and provide positive signals to investors. Activity, measured by Total Assets Turnover (TATO), has a negative direction and no significant effect on firm value, suggesting that asset utilization efficiency has not been a primary consideration for investors during the observation period. ESG shows a positive direction but does not significantly affect firm value, implying that although sustainability practices receive a favorable market response, their impact is not yet statistically strong. The robustness test confirms that activity and ESG remain insignificant, profitability and firm size remain significant, capital structure becomes insignificant under an alternative proxy, and the year dummy variables remain insignificant in both models.

5.2 Recommendations

The recommendations for future research are as follows. Future studies are encouraged to expand the sample by including more manufacturing firms as well as companies from other sectors, particularly by utilizing more comprehensive annual ESG data sources to improve data availability and enhance the generalizability of the findings. Researchers are also advised to use annual ESG scores throughout the observation period to better capture year-to-year changes in sustainability practices and obtain more accurate results. In addition, future research should consider conducting endogeneity tests to address the potential bidirectional relationship between capital structure and firm value, thereby ensuring more reliable causal inference in the estimation results.

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